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Review Article

Review On Preparation And Evaluation Of Moisturizing Cream

Kiran Gokul khandekar, Rahul Jagtap

Department Of Cosmetic Science Navsahyadri Institute Of Pharmacy Naigaon, Pune, Tal. Bhor, 412213

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ABSTRACT

Moisturizing cream are semi solids preparation used for reduces the chances of skin problems and fights wrinkles. The main aim of the research work is to prepare the moisturizing creams using different herbs and the prepared moisturizing cream are evaluated for the efficacy. The herbs used in the preparations are dried Ficus racemose leaves powder and cucumber peels the formulated moisturizing creams are evaluated for the various irritancy, washability, ph, viscosity, phase separation, spread ability, compatibility test. The results shown that all formulation gave satisfied results.

INTRODUCTION

Cream is a preparation usually for application to the skin. Creams are defining as "a semisolid dosage form containing one or more drug substances dissolved or dispersed in a suitable base "Creams are semi-solid emulsions of oil and water. O they are of a softer consistency & lighter body than true ointment. Semisolid emulsions of either o/w or w/o type. Moisturizer is a cosmetic preparation used for protecting, moisturizing, and lubricating the skin. These are creams which restore water (moisture) to the stratum corneum. Water contained in the cream is lost by evaporation when the cream is applied to the body. Moisturizers are complex mixtures of chemical agents often occlusive help hold water in the skin

after application, humectants attract moisture and emollients help smooth the skin.

Moisturizer cream is a skincare product used to hydrate and nourish the skin. It typically contains a combination of ingredients that help to increase the water content of the skin and prevent dryness, flakiness, and irritation. Moisturizer cream can be used on the face and body and is available in a range of formulas, including lightweight lotions, thicker creams, and balms. It is an essential component of a skincare routine, as it helps to maintain the skin's natural moisture barrier and improve its overall health and appearance.

CARE FOR DRY SKIN:

During the winter months, it's important to reach for skin care products that contain hydrating and

***Corresponding Author:** Kiran Gokul khandekar

Address: Department Of Cosmetic Science Navsahyadri Institute Of Pharmacy Naigaon, Pune, Tal. Bhor, 412213

Email ✉: kirankhandekar1261@gmail.com

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nourishing ingredients that will work hard for your skin to fight the weather's dehydrating effects. Most moisturizers contain a mixture of three groups of Humectants, Emollients, Occlusive.

The cosmetic industry describes the industry that manufactures and distributes cosmetic products. A cosmetic is any substance used to clean, improve or change the complexion, skin, hair, nails or teeth. Cosmetics include beauty preparations (make-up, perfume, skin cream, nail polish) and shampoo, shaving cream. It is primarily categorized into five major categories - body care, face care, hair care, hand care and colour cosmetics. Cosmetics are the preparations used to enhance the Human appearance.

The aim of the present research was to formulate the Moisturizing Cream for the purpose of Moistening, Nourishing, lightening & Treatment of various diseases of the skin.

Pharmaceutical industry discovers, develops, produces, and markets drugs or pharmaceutical drugs for use as medications to be administered to patients, with the aim to cure them, vaccinate them, or alleviate symptoms. Pharmaceutical companies may deal generic or brand medications and medical devices. To promote high standards in pharmaceutical product production, quality assurance and preparation of compound medicinal prescriptions, pharmaceutical and other appropriate products. (1)

ACTIVE PHARMACUTICAL INGREDIENT INTRODUCTION:

1) CUCUMBER

Occurrence And Distribution:

Europe, Asia, the Middle East, some parts of the U.S.A.

Taxonomical classification:

Botanical Name: Cucumis sativus Linn.

Local Name: Hindi- Khir Kingdome- Planate

Division - Angiosperms Class- Eudicots

Order- Cucurbitales

Family- Cucurbitaceae Subfamily- Cucurbitaceae

Genus- Cucumis

Species- C. sativus

Chemical Constituent of Cucumber: Cucumber, scientifically known as Cucumis sativus, contains various active chemical constituents that contribute to its health benefits. Some of the primary active constituents found in cucumber include:

1. **Cucurbitacins:** These are triterpenes found in cucumber, which have been shown to possess anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties.
 2. **Vitamins:** Cucumber contains various vitamins, including vitamin C, vitamin K, vitamin B5, and vitamin A, which are important for maintaining good health.
 3. **Minerals:** Cucumber is a good source of minerals, including magnesium, potassium, and manganese, which are essential for various bodily functions.
 4. **Flavonoids:** Cucumber contains flavonoids such as quercetin, apigenin, and kaempferol, which have antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties
 5. **Lignans:** Cucumber also contains lignans, such as pinosresinol and lariciresinol, which have been shown to have anti-cancer properties.
 6. **Water:** Cucumber is composed mostly of water, which makes it a hydrating food and helps to flush out toxins from the body
- These active constituents are responsible for the numerous health benefits associated with cucumber consumption, including improved digestion, reduced inflammation, and enhanced skin health.

USE:

- Cucumber helps keep the face fresh and glowing, owing to the silica and high-water content.
- Using cucumber slices on the eyes reduces puffiness and makes dark circles vanish from under the eyes.
- Do not discard cucumber peel it has many.

- Health benefits. The benefits include its beneficial.
- Effects in eye disorders, vitamin A & C deficiency.
- Constipation and bones and muscles disorder.
- Cucumber peels are rich in fiber and contain.
- minerals like magnesium, potassium, and silica.
- The silica is an essential component to keep your muscles, bones, and tendons healthy.
- hydrates our skin, improves complexion and vision.(2)

Pharmacological activity: Cucumbers have several pharmacological activities that are beneficial to human health. Some of these activities include:

1. Antioxidant activity: Cucumbers are a good source of antioxidants such as vitamin C and beta-carotene, which can help protect cells from damage caused by free radicals.
2. Anti-inflammatory activity: Cucumbers contain compounds such as cucurbitacins and flavonoids, which have anti-inflammatory properties. These compounds may help reduce inflammation in the body and alleviate symptoms of conditions such as arthritis.
3. Anti-cancer activity: Some studies suggest that cucumbers may have anti-cancer properties due to their high antioxidant content and ability to reduce inflammation.
4. Skin health activity: Cucumbers contain vitamins and minerals that are beneficial for skin health. For example, vitamin C can help promote collagen production, while silica can help strengthen connective tissues in the skin.

Overall, cucumbers are a nutritious and healthy food that can provide several pharmacological benefits. (3,4,5,6)

2) FICUS RACEMOSA

TAXONOMY

Kingdom: Plant Family
Classification: Magnoliophyta
Class: Magnolipsida
Order: Urticales
Family: Moraceae
Genus: Ficus
Species: racemosa.

Synonyms: - F. glomerata Roxb (7)

Chemical Constituent of ficus racemosa

Ficus racemosa, also known as the cluster fig tree, is a species of plant in the fig family. It has several active chemical constituents, including:

1. Ficusin - a flavonoid with anti-inflammatory properties.
2. Lupeol - a triterpenoid with anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer properties.
3. Psoralen - a furanocoumarin with anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties.
4. Bergapten - a furanocoumarin with antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties.

5. Quercetin - a flavonoid with antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-cancer properties.
6. Luteolin - a flavonoid with antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-cancer properties.
7. Kaempferol - a flavonoid with antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-cancer properties.
8. β -sitosterol - a phytosterol with cholesterol-lowering properties.

These active chemical constituents have been studied for their potential therapeutic benefits and may have applications in the treatment of various diseases and disorders. However, further research is needed to fully understand their mechanisms of action and potential clinical uses. (8,9,10)

- 1. Anti-inflammatory activity:** The ethanolic extract of *Ficus racemosa* has been found to possess anti-inflammatory activity in animal models. This activity is believed to be due to the presence of flavonoids, tannins, and other bioactive compounds.
- 2. Antioxidant activity:** *Ficus racemosa* is known to possess potent antioxidant activity due to the presence of phenolic compounds and flavonoids. These compounds scavenge free radicals and protect against oxidative damage.
- 3. Anti-cancer activity:** *Ficus racemosa* has been reported to possess anti-cancer

properties, particularly against breast cancer cells. The plant extract has been shown to induce cell death and inhibit the proliferation of cancer cells.

4. Wound healing activity

Stem bark ethanol extract showed healing in rat excision and incision wound models

5. Antifungal

Plants showed potent inhibitory activity against six fungi. *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, *Trichophyton rubrum*, *Trichophyton vocalis*, *Candida albicans*, *Candida cruzi* and *Torulopsis glabrata* (11,12,13,14,15)

Formula:

SR. NO	INGREDIENTS	FORMULATION	FORMULATION	FORMULATION
		F1	F2	F3
1	Cucumber extract	1ml	1.5 ml	1.9 ml
2	<i>Ficus racemosa</i> extract	1.1 ml	1.6 ml	2ml
3	Liquid paraffin	10 ml	21.32 ml	20.11
4	Borax	0.16 gm	0.56 gm	0.50 gm
5	Propyl paraben	0.02 gm	0.056 gm	0.50 gm
6	Rose oil	QS	QS	QS
7	Distilled water	QS	QS	QS

ROLE OF INGREDIENTS

SR. NO	INGREDIENTS	ROLE
1	Cucumber extract	moisturizer, reduce acne and pimples. Antioxidant
2	Ficus racemose extract	Antibacterial, Antifungal, anti-inflammatory
3	Liquid paraffin	Lubricating agent
4	Borax	Alkaline agent
5	Propyl paraben	Preservative
6	Rose oil	Fragrance
7	Distilled water	Vehicle

REFERENCES

- <https://www.slideshare.net/Ayanpal33/moisturizing-cream-ppt>
- Tripti Sahu*, Jyoti Sahu ISSN No. 2348 – 0335 Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Research www.japtronline.com.
- Hina Saeed, Anam Waheed ISSN No.: 2454-2024 (online) International Journal of Technical Research & Science.
- Tripathi KD, “Essentials of Medical Pharmacology”, 6th edition, Jaypee Brothers Medical, New Delhi, 2008, 185.
- Rang HP, Dale MM, “Pharmacology”, 6th Edition, Churchill Livingstone Elsevier, 2007, 502-3
- Ankita S., Kaur P., and Gupta R. Phytochemical screening and antimicrobial assay of various seeds extracts of Cucurbitaceae Family. International Journal of Applied Biology & Pharmaceutical Technology. Volume 3, Issue 3 (2012): 401-409
- Sasaki YF, Kawaguchi S, Kamaya A, Ohshita M, Kabasawa K, Iwama K et al. 2002 Mutation Research/Genetic Toxicology and Environmental Mutagenesis.; 519(1):103-119.
- Cai Y, Luo Q, Sun M, Corke H. Life Sci. 2004; 74(171):2157-2184. Antioxidant activity and phenolic compounds of 112 traditional Chinese medicinal plants associated with anticancer.
- Sumi SA, Siraj MA, Hossain A, Mia MS, Afrin S, Rahman MM. Med. 2016 Investigation of the Key Pharmacological Activities of Ficus racemosa and Analysis of Its Major Bioactive Polyphenols by HPLC-DAD. Evidence-Based Complement. Altern.
- Prakash Deep, Amrit Kr. Singh, Md. Tahir Ansari, Prashant Raghav, Sep – Oct 2013; Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Rev. Res., 22(1), n° 06, 29-34 ISSN 0976 – 044X
- IJCRT1813121 International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT) www.ijcrt.org
- Biswas TK, Mukherjee B, Plant medicines of Indian origin for wound healing activity: a review. Int J Low Extreme Wounds, 2, 2003, 25- 39.
- Deraniyagala SA, Wijesundera RLC, Weerasena OVD, Antifungal activity of Ficus racemosa leaf extract and isolation of the active compound, J Nat Sci Counc Sri Lanka, 26, 1998, 19-26.
- ISSN: 1388-0209 (Print) 1744-5116 (Online) Journal homepage: <https://www.tandfonline.com/loi/iphb20>
- <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330956326>
- <https://chat.openai.com/?model=text-davinci-002-render>
- A.U. Adamu, Y. Abdulmumin, RK Mustapha, J. Mater. Environ. Sci., 2021, Volume 12, Issue 12, Page 1627-1636, Journal of Materials and

Environmental Science ISSN: 2028-2508CODEN: JMESCN,

<http://www.jmaterenvironsci.com>

18. Sunil H. Ganatra, Shweta P. Durge, Patil S. U., ISSN : 0975-7384CODEN(USA)

:JCPRC5, Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research,2012,4(5):2380-2384 , www.jocpr.com

19. Dr. Supriya Yadav, Dr. VK Gupta, Dr. A Gopalakrishnan and Dr. Med Ram Verma,

Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies 2019; 7(1): 1443-1446

20. Bhavana Patil, Neha Yadav, Gopal Yadav, Shrikesh Yadav, Suraj Yadav,Dr. Smita Takarkhede© 2022 JETIR March 2022, Volume 9, Issue 3www.jetir.org (ISSN-2349-5162)

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